

On extensions $\varphi(X)$ and $v(X)$ of inverse semigroups X

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In the talk we shall discuss the algebraic structure of various extensions of an inverse semigroup X and detect semigroups whose extensions $\varphi(X)$ and $v(X)$ are inverse semigroups.

Theorem 1. *For a semigroup X and its semigroup of filters $\varphi(X)$ the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $\varphi(X)$ is a commutative Clifford semigroup;
- (2) $\varphi(X)$ is an inverse semigroup;
- (3) the idempotents of the semigroup $\varphi(X)$ commute and $\varphi(X)$ is sub-Clifford or regular in $N_2(X)$;
- (4) X is isomorphic to one of the semigroups: C_2 , L_n or $L_n \sqcup C_2$ for some $n \in \omega$.

Theorem 2. *For a semigroup X and its semigroup of upfamilies $v(X)$ the following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $v(X)$ is a finite semilattice;
- (2) $v(X)$ is an inverse semigroup;
- (3) the idempotents of the semigroup $v(X)$ commute and $v(X)$ is sub-Clifford or regular;
- (4) X is a finite linear semilattice, isomorphic to L_n for some $n \in \omega$.

References

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